

Human Factors Issues and Measures in Advanced NPPs

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Abstract : Various advanced technologies will be adopted in Advanced Control Rooms (ACRs) of advanced Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs), which is thought to increase operators' performance. However, potential human factors issues coupled with digital technologies might be troublesome. Human factors issues in ACRs are identified and strategies (or countermeasures) for evaluating and analyzing each of issues are addressed in this study.

Keywords : advanced control room, human factor issues, human performance, human error, nuclear power plant

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